

SOCIAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY IN MODERN EDUCATION ADMINISTRATION

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Abstract

Technologies play an important role in the administration of modern education, we become education administrators in pre-school, general education, professional and higher educational institutions, which play an important role in the successful implementation of educational activities.

It should be noted that in recent years, technologies in education and in particular in education administration have brought about a great revolution, completely changing the activities of educational institutions. Changed communication, facilitated collaboration between stakeholders. Now, through various platforms, administrators can collaborate with colleagues, students, faculty, and facilitate the dissemination of information to the general public, which enhances inclusivity and accessibility. Technologies help the administrator to collect, analyze a large amount of data and plan strategic steps. Also, it allows predicting future needs. However, along with various positive environments, there are challenges, risks, even such as the issue of confidentiality, the need for continuous professional development, etc. However, all challenges require the employer to have a strong data privacy policy, ongoing training, retraining opportunities and access to technological resources.

The purpose of this paper is to study the history of modern education administration, to study the role of technology, to analyze challenges and future perspectives. Accordingly, the paper examines the role of technology in education administration.

Keywords: technologies, educational institution, education administrator, modern challenges.

Introduction

Today, the growing role of technology in the field of education is significantly noticeable. Educational institutions use technology-based administrative management systems for tasks that, on the one hand, improve administrative processes and promote operational efficiency. Technology ensures collaboration and seamless communication between lecturers, students, teachers, parents.

Educational administration involves the management and organization of educational institutions, such as schools, colleges, institutions of higher education, or other entities. It addresses various administrative tasks, resource management, strategic planning, monitoring, policy implementation. Education administrators play an important role in facilitating the smooth functioning of an educational institution.

In Georgia, there are master's programs in education administration, the graduate of which passes with a certain result, such as knowledge of modern international and local trends in the development of the field of education, educational policy, governance structure, funding models, educational teaching theories, curriculum development principles, educational leadership principles, organizational management theories. Must have the ability to create a positive organizational environment and culture, academic integrity, research planning and implementation, including the ability to use modern information and communication technologies in the management process. If we take a look at the Georgian labor market and the areas where education administration graduates are needed, we will see that the use of technology is strongly required, and as time passes, it is becoming more and more a part of modern education, which revolutionized the process of teaching, learning and administrative activities.

It should be noted that over time education administration developed significantly, different structural units were formed, it became necessary to adapt technologies, to adapt to the needs of different students. However, despite technological advances, many educational institutions today still continue to practice traditional administrative practices such as paper-based record keeping.

Educational administrators today face many challenges in running an educational institution, including limited resources, complex regulatory requirements, student needs, and more. And technology offers opportunities for routine tasks, big data analysis, information delivery. Effective communication and cooperation are essential for the operation of an educational institution. Technology helps administrators, teachers, students, pupils and parents to communicate through various channels such as email, online collaboration platforms.

Administrators in educational institutions work with large amounts of data related to student performance, attendance, and resource use. And technology allows administration and administrators to collect, store, analyze and use data and monitor progress.

In the field of education, we often face barriers in adapting to change, but in this changing world, the role of the administrator is to maximize the ability to convert innovations into perspectives. Despite various challenges, the public's different view of educational technologies remains relevant, some believe that there are a number of challenges related to confidentiality, unequal resources and lack of awareness, while some characterize the role of technology positively, therefore, based on the relevance of the topic, the purpose of our research is to study the history of modern education administration, the role of technology Study, analysis of challenges and future perspectives.

It is important to study educational institutions, identify successful practices, and explore emerging technologies that have potential for the future of education administration, which discusses innovation, artificial intelligence, applications, and more.

Accordingly, the tasks of our research are:

- To determine the practical use of technologies in education administration;
- Identify the challenges, barriers and opportunities to adapt technology in education administration;
- To present recommendations regarding effective use of technologies.

Based on the aim and objectives, the practical novelty of our study is to find out how modern technologies change the activities of the educational administrator, the developed recommendations will be able to be used for all interested persons and educational administration master's programs.

Based on the above, the hypothesis of our research is, "The integration of technologies in education administration has improved the performance of the administrator".

The object of the research in the current study is the education administrators of USD, with whom an in-depth interview was conducted.

Technology in Education

Technology plays a crucial role in modern education administration. By strategically leveraging technology, educational institutions can streamline admissions processes, enhance collaboration, and ultimately improve outcomes. However, a predetermined plan, institutions in infrastructure and continuous professional development of stakeholders are important.

We know that the first industrial revolution was the invention of water and steam in industry, and then there was the promotion of mass production with the help of electricity. Electronic and information mechanisms were created during the third revolution. And now, on the basis of the third, the fourth digital revolution is underway.

Compared to previous industries, today's technological stage is developing at an incredible speed. It changes the activities of different countries, different fields, in particular, it made important changes in the field of education. Distance learning in particular has left a significant mark on many industries, including education.

What are educational technologies? - Educational technologies are designed to improve teaching-learning and administrative activities, which include different tools and resources. Such can be Moodle, Canva, smart boards, postcasts, webinars and other management sys-

tems, which together have a positive impact on educational activities. There are various educational applications that facilitate interactive learning, or even online courses that help us update our knowledge without leaving home. Noting the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in education, AI-powered tools enable insights into student performance. Also, platforms such as Microsoft Teams and others allow collaboration.

All these technologies are being developed, improved and made available for the educational space every day. There are information systems, learning management systems that simplify the performance of administrative tasks.

Educational technology enables administrators to streamline operations, even using different data to identify trends, make new decisions, and motivate and support students. Moreover, digital communication tools such as e-mail, messaging platforms, and similar tools help the administrator to communicate effectively with colleagues, students, and the community of interest, which promotes teamwork. Technologies provide budget management, cost accounting, and efficient allocation of resources. Social networks connect administrators with colleagues, other international organizations around the world, provide an opportunity to seek advice and deepen cooperation. Also, it can be said that online platforms, in addition to simplifying the process of administrators, help administrators to retrain, learn new knowledge, offer them to easily engage in professional development activities.

A qualitative research report

Based on the theoretical material presented above, a qualitative study was carried out to find out - "how educational administrators evaluate the use of technology in their work". The research was carried out on the basis of targeted sampling, with respondents employed in 8 different positions in 4 universities.

The services of the mentioned respondents were represented by the Quality Assurance Department, Career Development and Alumni Relations Department, Administration Department, Financial Affairs Department, Examination Service and the Faculty, employees of such services that have to perform administrative activities using technologies.

We asked how often they used technologies, platforms, and applications in their educational activities, and most of them answered that they use them in their daily life. None of the respondents were unfamiliar with the definition of educational technologies.

We asked the respondents to give practical examples of the use of technology in their work, to which we received varied answers from administrators that when they want to share information with students, provide news, they always use technology, even to post news on the website. Respondents say that the 21st century is unimaginable without technology, that difficult everyday work can be done in simple ways thanks to technology. They talk about everything from the Internet/computer to educational bases, as well as applications, web pages that improve daily activities and differentiate the administrator of the previous century from the functions of the administrator of today.

We also asked what barriers educational institutions face when using technology, and the majority cited a lack of awareness among employees.

Also, according to all interviewed respondents, technologies in terms of improving the quality of administration in education simplify the activity and make it positive.

In order to ensure the effective and ethical use of educational technologies, relevant bases, platforms, what measures are needed in this regard, we received interesting answers that it is necessary to increase awareness, improve technical skills, that appropriate technologies should be used in the educational space, personnel should be retrained, trained, employers should Personal security information should be shared. One of the respondents noted that people employed in an educational institution should already be familiar with the use of educational technologies and should have the ability to be versatile, easily able to adapt to innovations, especially in this changing world. Often older generations ignore modern approaches and do not use innovations that actually simplify everyday life. It turned out that it is mainly the employer's obligation to provide employees with constant information and news.

We also asked educational administrators what technological recommendations they would make to improve administrative practices. The respondents

share information about continuous education and tell us that an employee, especially in the field of education, must constantly take care of updating knowledge, adaptability, acceptance of news, must be involved in the development process, that the use of technologies to improve activities is one of the necessary conditions, since by using technologies, the education administrator can carry out such activities. The implementation can be such as:

- planning and managing the educational process;
- Creation of news/innovations - analysis of data collected on the basis of electronic surveys, planning and implementation of news;
- Conducting webinars/trainings on various necessary topics, both for cooperation and students, as well as for interested persons;
- Finding, adapting and offering different platforms to the university;
- Performing many other useful activities.

Finally, we asked what they thought were the main factors that lead to the successful integration of technology in education administration, which most people say is the need for mutual willingness on the part of the employee and the employer, motivation, constant concern for development and openness. Also, it is said that simplicity, speed and flexibility affect the integration of technologies. One of the respondents points out that in order to integrate technologies in the educational field, it is necessary to have a sound infrastructure, a sufficient number of technologies, good Internet, appropriate software, access to educational programs on platforms, and therefore technological implementation of administrative activities saves a lot of time and environmental resources.

Educational technology helps administrators make data-driven decisions and create better learning environments that meet the needs of all students, enabling them to plan and implement positive change.

Conclusion

Based on the material we found and the research conducted, the goal has been achieved and it is certain how the role of technology is evaluated by the administrators of modern education. Therefore, the role of technology in modern education administration is multifaceted. It includes communication, data management, decision making and most importantly increasing efficiency. By using technology, educational institutions can adapt to evolving requirements, improve organizational efficiency.

The modern administrators were familiar with the interpretation of technologies, their use, the production of different platforms and bases, moreover, they had a complete understanding of artificial intelligence. The respondents talked about challenges and shortcomings, that technologies have a great opportunity to improve living conditions, with their help it becomes possible to create and develop new products. With the help of technology, lecturers are given the opportunity to correct the student's work online, easily reflect the scores in the databases, send the leave request online, which also gives the opportunity to do things without leaving home.

Technology in modern education administration enables efficiency, innovation, and promotes equity. Using it, administrators can optimize their activities, implement positive changes. It offers various opportunities to improve efficiency, strengthen communication. With the help of this, educational institutions can allocate resources, save time, and perform effective activities. However, there are issues that need to be addressed, such as digital equality, organizational resistance and facilitating adaptation to change.

We need to create future-oriented educational programs that prepare educational administrators to easily adapt to modern challenges. We must create a future that will benefit everyone. Although we may be in danger of 'robotizing' humans in current processes, we must use technology to our advantage and bring out the best in humans.

Accordingly, for the integration of technologies and the improved performance of the tasks of the education administrator, we present the recommendations obtained as a result of the research:

- providing administrators with trainings from the side of the employer;
- Use of technologies in educational institutions, formation of policy regarding ethical and personal information;
- constant monitoring regarding the use of technologies and administrator's activities;
- Introduction of incentive mechanisms.

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